

STUDY OF SLIDING FRICTION AND WEAR PROPERTIES OF BISMALIMIDE AND ITS COMPOSITE AGAINST AL

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SUMMARY: Bismaleimide is a kind of thermosetting resin developed in 1970s, it has got the wide application in engineering field and aviation technology. However, its friction and wear properties, such as the influences of inorganic packings on its tribological characteristics, are not yet reported in current references. In order to develop a particular organic frictional material, a new bismaleimide was chosen. Under test, it was discovered that dry frictional coefficient of bismaleimide was higher but decreased with time and adhesive wear occurred between the bismaleimide and some metals. For the sake of improving its tribological characteristics, three kinds of inorganic fillers, namely CuO, Sillimanite and Wollastonite, were chosen as frictional modifier. The influences of the concentration of these fillers and the size of Sillimanite and wollastonite on sliding frictional properties of bismaleimide against hard AL (LY 12) were studied respectively with a ring-on-ring tribological machine and the modified mechanisms of these fillers were investigated primarily.

KEYWORDS: CuO, sillimanite, wollastonite, bismaleimide, friction material

INTRODUCTION

The friction and wear properties of polymer-based composite filled by inorganic packings have been studied frequently by scholars in tribology field. The fillers such as metal powder, oxide and other inorganic chemical compounds have been studied carefully, while the study on some natural mineral as filler is seldom done. The study on polymer has been mainly focused on thermoplastic polymers[1-5] such as HDPE, PTFE, PI, PA11 and PEEK, while the study on other kinds of polymers, especially thermosetting polymer is hardly done[6-7]. There are many opinions on the mechanism of friction and wear effects of fillers on polymers, but consistent conclusion has not been achieved until now[8].

Bismaleimide which is a new kind of thermosetting resin, has got wide applications in aviation and spaceflight industry field at first, and then, widely used in civil industry as engineering plastic with high temperature resistance in recent years. It has not only the superior properties, such as resistance to high temperature and humidity, high modulus of elasticity, moderate hardness, and high adhesive reliability to inorganic materials, but also it can be produced by the forming process similar to that of epoxy resin, which makes its production costs come down. In particular, it's supposed to be an adhesive to organic frictional materials[9], because its temperature resistance is superior to that of phenolic resin.

However, there is little research done in the field of friction and wear characteristics of BMI, especially the field of inorganic fillers; influence on its tribological characteristics.

In order to develop a special organic frictional material, a new kind of bismaleimide was selected as adhesive. The experiment on pure BMI polymer showed that its dry frictional coefficient was high, but the coefficient decreased with time. Furthermore, adhesive wear occurred between the bismaleimide and dual metals. Therefore, three kinds of inorganic fillers, namely CuO, sillimanite and wollastonite, were chosen as frictional modifier. Sillimanite and wollastonite which is abundant is two kinds of natural mineral fillers with low price. When BMI is filled by them, the composite's cost is lowered while properties improved. CuO is kind of inorganic chemical compound which has been studied carefully. It has been found out that when CuO is filled in thermoplastic polymer, the wear resistance is raised, so is their frictional coefficient[4-5]. But the influences when BMI is filled by CuO, are not yet reported in current references.

EXPERIMENT

Sample Preparation

Sample ingredient: three portions of sillimanite powder with the size of 100#, 200# and 300# respectively, main ingredient: AL₂O₃ and SiO₂, hardness: 6.5-7.0 Mohs; three portions of wollastonite powder with the size of 400#, 800# and 2000# respectively, main ingredient: SiO₂ and CaO, hardness: 4.5 Mohs; hardness of CuO: 3-3.5 Mohs; bismaleimide HF-9401 (BMI), hardness: HRM122

Sample making: These powder of wollastonite and sillimanite was rinsed with the mixture of alcohol and acetone, then was dried out. In proportion as weight, take 100 portions of BMI, 5, 10, 15, 20 portions of four concentrations of sillimanite respectively, 50, 100, 200 portions of three concentrations of wollastonite respectively, and mix them according to different size of powder, then using pressing method, produce biphase system circular BMI sample, the size of which is . Polish the top and bottom surface of the sample with 600# and 800# water sand paper respectively, rinse it with alcohol repeatedly, then finish making sample by drying it.

Experiment Procedure

The sliding test was accomplished with a ring-on-ring tribological machine MPX-200. The upper ring which rubbed against the composite sample was hard AL (LY12). Its size was with two edge sides polished with 800# water sand paper. It had been rinsed and dried before the experiment. The vertical pressure: 60N. The speed of main shaft: 370rpm. The duration of experimental time: 30min. Wear volume of the sample was measured by the weight difference before and after experiment, with precision of 0.0001g. The unit of wear rate is g/Nmm in this paper. The experiment was done in a state of dry friction under indoor temperature.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Influence of CuO on the Friction and Wear Properties of Bismaleimide

As fig.1 shows, when BMI was filled by CuO, the frictional coefficient between the binary composite and AL ring tended to rise with the increasing of CuO weight fraction, while the

wear rate between them tended to decrease. But there was little influence on the wear rate when the concentration of CuO was over 25 wt%. The cause of the phenomenon referred above is that CuO filled in BMI promotes the formation of the transfer film on the AL, as a result, the adhesive wear tendency liable to happen between pure BMI and AL ring declines. Under test, observing the surface appearance of AL ring which had rubbed against BMI which was filled by CuO, a layer of well-distributed black transfer matter which couldn't be cleaned up by absorbent cotton could be found. This shows transfer film has been formed and adhered tightly to AL ring. It's the protection of the transfer film on AL ring that make AL ring's wear rate drop. The wear resistance of the transfer film restrains the wear caused by the matter transfer on the composite's surface, and thus, decrease its wear rate. Friction and wear takes place between BMI's composite and the transfer film, the friction and wear model of which is shown in Fig.2, and there is strong molecular force between them. Furthermore, because CuO fraction is a substance with hardness, when it is filled in BMI, the mechanic meshing effect between the frictional pairs is strengthened. In conclusion, the increasing of both the mechanic effect and molecular force between the frictional pairs leads to the rise of friction coefficient between the composite and AL ring.

Fig. 1: Variation of wear rate and friction coefficient of BMI composite and AL ring with CuO weight fraction 1.BMI composite 2.AL ring 3.friction coefficient

Fig.2 The sliding model of BMI composite filled by CuO against AL.

The effects of CuO have also been verified by Bahadure[4-5]. They found through experiment, the friction coefficient and wear resistance of thermoplastic polymer wear raised when CuO was filled in the polymer. The study in this paper shows the effects of CuO may be similar to different kinds of polymer.

Influence of Wollastonite on the Friction and Wear Properties of Bismaleimide

As Fig.3 shows, when BMI was filled by wollastonite powder, the frictional coefficient of BMI drops with the increase of wollastonite concentration. In addition, the antifriction effect of wollastonite on BMI was different according to the size of wollastonite powder. The size is larger, the decline of the friction coefficient is less.

Fig.3 Variation of friction coefficient of BMI composite with wollastonite weight fraction.

□ pure BMI , ▨ 400[#]wollastonite
 ≡ 800[#], ▩ 2000[#]

Figure 4: Variation of wear rate of BMI composite with wollastonite weight fraction

□ pure BMI , ▨ 400[#]wollastonite
 ▩ 800[#], ▧ 2000[#]

Figure 5: Variation of wear rate of AL ring with wollastonite weight fraction

□ pure BMI , ▨ 400[#]wollastonite
 ▩ 800[#], ▧ 2000[#]

As Fig.4 and Fig.5 show, when wollastonite powder was filled in BMI, the wear rate of BMI and the AL ring dropped obviously. Moreover, the antifriction effect was raised with the increasing concentration and decreasing size of wollastonite powder. But it's difficult for the wollastonite powder to be well distributed when it is ground mixedly, if the size of the

powder is too small. The wear resistance effect of wollastonite powder thanks to the inorganic filler's short-fiber structure with length and diameter in a ratio of 5:1-15:1. It's main ingredient is CaO and SiO₂. As referred above, the rub of pure BMI against AL ring is in the form of adhering transfer film which is not firm. When wollastonite powder is filled, in the break strength of the composite is raisen. In addition, the slender and hard particles of wollastonite cause polishing effect, which makes the oxidic film on the surface of AL ring peeled off and fresh surface exposed. CaO and SiO₂ which are composed of wollastonite can promote the formation of transfer film and the film's adherence of AL ring, which makes the film firm[8]. The wear of AL ring is allieviated because the sliding friction is between the surfaces of the transfer film and BMI's composite. Moreover, the wear resistance of the composite is raisen because the film which is firm and hard to wear away, prevent the further wear of the composite. Observed after experiment, the analysis above can be confirmed by the brown transfer film on the surface of AL ring and such smooth frictional surface appearance of BMI's composite as Fig.6 shows.

a) AL ring

b) BMI composite

Fig. 6: Optical micrographs of wear of BMI composite and AL ring surface (arrow indicating sliding direction x500)

Influence of Sillimanite on the Friction and Wear Properties of Bismaleimide

As shown in Fig.7, the frictional coefficient of the compound system was raised with the increasing of concentration and size of the sillmanite powder filled in BMI. Fig.8 shows the variation of the frictional coefficient of BMI's compoite filled by 200# sillimanite with time, from which we learn the fact that the frictional coefficient of pure BMI increases first with time to a high value, then decline gradually and the variation is not stable. When sillimanite was filled, the frictional coefficient in a stable state was raised, the tribological characteristics were improved. The frictional coefficient increased with time and remained steady when it had risen to a high value. However it took longer to reach the stable state of friction if the concentration of sillimanite increased.

Fig. 7: Effect of sillimanite weight fraction on friction coefficient of BMI composite.
1. 100# sillimanite 2. 200# sillimanite 3. 300# sillimanite

Fig. 8: Variation of friction coefficient of BMI composite filled by 200# size sillimanite with time. 1. Pure BMI 2. BMI + 5% sillimanite 3. BMI + 10% 4. BMI + 15%

The main reason of the phenomenon referred above is, if sillimanite which is rigid particle with high hardness filled in BMI, it is analogous to scatter relatively hard particles to soft basic body, therefore, sillimanite particles on sliding surface do great damage to the transfer film which influence the frictional stability. The sliding model is shown in fig.9. In addition, the uneven surface of the composite which is due to the different wear volume between the soft and hard materials strengthens mechanic meshing effect when rubbed against AL ring. Consequently, the frictional coefficient of BMI's composite raises, and then tends to be stable. The wear resistance of the composite is raised. Furthermore, as fig.10 shows, the wear rate is less, the rise of wear resistance is more remarkable, with the increasing of sillimanite concentration and its size. But it's not suitable if the concentration of sillimanite is too much, otherwise, it'll take longer for frictional coefficient to reach stability and the wear of dual AL ring will be grave. Under test, it's found if the content of sillimanite is over 15%, the wear of AL ring is serious, and the wear rate of AL ring against BMI filled by sillimanite is high than

that AL ring against pure BMI. Therefore, if the frictional material against AL ring is to be made, the content of sillimanite in the material is not suitable to be over 10%.

The main reason that sillimanite can improve BMI's composite's properties of wear resistance is analysed as the following. Sillimanite, the crystalline grain of which is needlelike has high ability to adhere to BMI resin and the adhesive strength is fairly high. The sillimanite particles on the sliding surface sustain the load in the process of friction, which decreases alleviates the wear of the basic bldy. In addition, it will cost much frictional work to remove the sillimanite particles from basic body. Therefore, the wear resistance of BMI's composite filled by sillimanite is raised and the effect is more notable with increasing of the concentration and size of sillimanite. In the process of friction, because sillimanite is harder than AL, its partides which have been filled in BMI on the sliding surface destroy the formation of the transfer film and its protective effect. Moreover, grave ploughing wear occures on the relatively soft basic body of AL ring, which makes its wear rate increase.

Figure. 9: The sliding model of BMI composite filled by sillimanite against AL.

Fig. 10: Variation of wear rate of BMI composite and AL ring with sillimanite weight fraction. ● 100[#] sillimanite, × 200[#], ▲ 300[#]

CONCLUSION

1. Wollastonite, CuO and sillimanite, all of them can improve the wear resistance of BMI, and they are listed in an order from strong effect to weak one. CuO and sillimanite can raise the frictional coefficient of BMI, and sillimanite can also improve BMI's tribological characteristics.
2. The fact that wollastonite and CuO can improve the wear resistance of BMI and AL ring, mainly relates to the protective transfer film. CaO and SiO₂ in both CuO and wollastonite can promote the formation of the film, which makes its adhesive strength to basic body rise. Sillimanite can improve the wear resistance of BMI. Its mechanism is that the load is sustained by particles with high hardness, consequently, the wear of BMI is prevented. However, the wear of AL ring is raised because ploughing effect of hard particles destroys the formation of transfer film.
3. The frictional coefficient and wear resistance of BMI and AL ring is raised with the accumulation of CuO's concentration, while the rise slows down when the concentration is over 30 portions. As far as wollastonite is concerned, the wear resistance of BMI and AL ring is raised while the frictional coefficient between them declines with the increasing concentration and decreasing size of wollastonite. Moreover, the difference of the influence is little when the concentration is over 100 portions. The influence is almost identical when the size of wollastonite is 800# and 2000#. However, it's suitable to choose the size of 800# when well-distribute extent is taken into account. although sillimanite which is inorganic particles with high hardness can improve the wear resistance and frictional coefficient of BMI with the increasing of its concentration and size, the wear of the AL ring against BMI filled by sillimanite is aggravated. Therefore, its concentration should not exceed 10 portions and it's suitable to choose its size of 200#.

REFERENCES

1. B.J.Briscoe, A.K.Podosian and D.Tabor, The friction and wear of HDPE: the action of lead oxide and copper oxide fillers, wear, Vol.27, 1974, pp.19-34.
2. K.Tanaka and S.Kawakami, Effect of various fillers on the friction and wear of PTFE-based composites, wear, Vol.79, 1982, pp221-234.
3. K.Friedrich, Sliding wear performance of different polyimide formulations, Tribol. Int.,22(1989),pp.25-31.
4. S.Bahadur and D.Gong, The role of copper compounds as fillers in the transfer and wear behavior of PEEK, wear, 154(1992), pp.151-165.
5. S.Bahadur and D.Gong, The role of copper compounds as fillers in the transfer film formation and wear of nylon, wear, 154(1992), pp.207-223.
6. S.K.Rhee, Friction properties of a phenolic resin filled with iron and graphite-sensitivity to load, speed and temperature, wear, 28(1974), pp. 277-281.

7. Qu Jianjun, Zhang Yafeng, Zhang Zhi qian and Qi Yu Lin, Effect of two kinds of inorganic fillers on the friction and wear properties of sillmanite, *Mechanic Engeering, appending magazine* (1995), pp.11-12.
8. S.Bahadur and D.Gong, The action of fillers in the modification of the tribological behavior of polymers, *wear*, 158(1992), pp. 41-59.
9. Bai Yongping, Study of composite modified by sillimanite-based resin, [academic paper], Harbin: Harbin Institute of Technology.
10. S.Bahadur and D.Gong The role of copper compounds as filers in the transfer and wear behavior of polyetheretherketone. *wear* 154(1992), pp. 151-165.
11. Fiduothic. *Modern frictional materials*, translated by Xu Run, Bei Jing: Metallurgy industry press, 1983, pp. 150-200.